

Appendix A

Assessment Rubric for the Learning Unit Assignment (UDA)

Dimensions	Criteria	Advanced	Intermediate	Basic	Emerging
Basic design of the Learning Unit (UDA)	Completeness, coherence, and conciseness in describing the context, defining objectives, and structuring the phases	The learning unit is designed in a concise, complete, and coherent way: the context is described accurately and appropriately; objectives are specific and observable; phases are clearly structured with suitable timing, resources, and methodologies.	The learning unit is clearly designed, although some elements are only partially developed.	The learning unit is present but described in a general and insufficiently articulated manner.	The learning unit is fragmented, incoherent, or lacks essential elements.
Design of assessment practices	Completeness, articulation, theoretical justification, and integration of assessment functions (formative, summative, and assessment for learning)	The assessment design is comprehensive and well articulated, supported by relevant theoretical discussion, and integrates all assessment functions.	The assessment design is coherent and present, with a good level of theoretical argumentation, although not always developed in depth.	The assessment design is mainly descriptive, with limited theoretical support and attention to only a few aspects.	The assessment design is superficial and poorly aligned with the intended objectives.
Assessment tools and transparency	Appropriateness, clarity, coherence, and purpose of the assessment tools used	Assessment tools are appropriate, well designed, clearly described, and consistently aligned with the objectives and assessment practices.	Assessment tools are appropriate but insufficiently justified or only partially described.	Assessment tools are present but generic or not always relevant.	Assessment tools are inadequate.
Students' active participation in assessment	Presence and quality of exemplars, self-assessment, peer assessment, and shared construction of criteria	Active participation is well structured, with meaningful exemplars, shared rubrics, and integrated self-assessment and peer assessment practices.	Some active participation practices are present, but they are not fully articulated or coherent.	Only one form of active participation is present, with no integration into the assessment process.	Students' active participation is very superficial and poorly aligned with the proposed work.

